

DIAGNOSTICS OF SOCIAL TOLERANCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the results of diagnostic research on students' tolerance and its manifestations on the subscales "Social tolerance", "Ethnic tolerance", and "Tolerance as a personal trait".

Keywords: tolerance, social tolerance, ethnic tolerance, personal tolerance.

ДИАГНОСТИКА СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о результатах диагностического исследования толерантности студентов и ее проявлений по субшкалам «Социальная толерантность», «Этническая толерантность», «Толерантность как черта личности».

Ключевые слова: толерантность, социальная толерантность, этническая толерантность, личная толерантность.

INTRODUCTION

Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farobi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Unsurul Maoli Kaikovus, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, Alisher Navoi, Abdullah Awlani studied the issue of educating a perfect person and educating them in the spirit of tolerance. Philosophers, sociologists, psychologists I.Karimov, Z.R.Kadirova, A.J.Sharipov, V.AAlimasov, Sh.O.Madaeva, E.K.Karimova, Z.Husniddinov, N.S.Safaev, A. The works of scientists such as G. Asmolov, B. E. Riordon, and R. R. Valitova explain the philosophical, sociological and psychological aspects of tolerance.

Pedagogical scientists D. J. Sharipova, M. Kuronov, V. Andriyanova, F. R. Kadirova, G. Akramova, R. Meditova, Z. Salieva, G. Aripova, B. S. Gershunsky, O. B. Skryabina, In the works of V.S. Kukushin, O.O. Kahenko, I.V. Mirotvorskaya, the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the virtue of tolerance in students at various stages of education are highlighted.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the world, one of the priority areas is the development of tolerance at the level of the state, social groups, and individual citizens. Its solution includes the development of regulatory and legal frameworks that regulate the tolerant behavior of relevant citizens, the implementation of special social and educational programs that contribute to strengthening the values of tolerance, as well as the implementation of interdisciplinary scientific research on the problems of forming the consciousness of tolerance in citizens.

The widespread use of the concept of "tolerance" by politicians, journalists, and scientists around the world, as well as the results of the study of the interdisciplinary, multifaceted problem of tolerance, allow us to reveal controversial issues related to defining its essence. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the study of tolerance depend on the concept of tolerance in social relations and the actual problems of social relations.

RESULTS

The survey material consisted of statements reflecting the general attitude to the surrounding world and other people, as well as social relations in various spheres of human interaction in which tolerance and intolerance are manifested. The methodology includes

affirmations that include attitudes towards certain social groups (the mentally ill, people of other religions and races, the poor), attitudes towards communication (respect for the opinions of others, willingness to resolve conflicts constructively, and effective cooperation). The survey focused on attitudes towards people, other racial and ethnic groups. Three subscales of the Tolerance Questionnaire; ethnic tolerance, social tolerance, tolerance is aimed at diagnosis as a personality trait. We made some changes to the questionnaire for students and young people based on national characteristics. The questionnaire includes 21 questions. To these questions, test-takers answer "I completely disagree", "I disagree", "I partially disagree", "I partially agree", "I agree", "I completely agree".

The student period corresponds to the period of adolescence. While the period of adolescence is divided into two stages in psychology, in a general sense, this period is recognized as a new stage of the formation of a person's life position. That is why the beginning of this period is early adolescence, which is defined as the "threshold of maturity". This stage of maturity includes physiological, psychological and social boundaries. The acquisition of "adult" social status by adolescents, the concrete content of this period of development is primarily determined by social conditions. The role of young people in society, their position, the amount of knowledge they acquire and a number of other factors depend on social conditions. Adolescence is a period of formation of a person as a citizen, his social development, self-determination of his own destiny, active participation in social life, and the formation of moral qualities of a citizen and a patriot. It is important socio-psychological importance to study whether the characteristics of social tolerance are formed in the student age and to research the psychological methods of its development.

DISCUSSION

The concept of "tolerance" has been formed for many centuries and is being filled with various symbols even now. The concept of tolerance is manifested in different forms in connection with different cultures and people's historical experience. In the dictionaries published in the Uzbek language, it is noticeable that the concept of "tolerance" is used as a synonym for the concept of "tolerance": "Tolerance is a concept that expresses people who are kind, caring, generous, and generous towards others, who have such spiritual qualities. Tolerance means respecting other people's worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic characteristics, traditions and rituals, not allowing discrimination and insults in dealings, considering humanity above all else and observing it in the community, workplaces, and neighborhoods.

In our conducted research, students' characteristics on the scales of "Ethnic tolerance", "Social tolerance" and "Tolerance as a personal trait" were revealed.

We used the following subscales in qualitative analysis of students' tolerance aspects:

I. Ethnic tolerance

The sub-scale "Ethnic tolerance" reveals the individual's attitude towards him, manifested in interactions with representatives of other ethnic groups and relations in the intercultural sphere.

II. Social tolerance

The subscale "Social tolerance" allows to study the tolerance of intolerance towards different social groups, as well as the relationship of personal relations with certain social processes.

III. Tolerance as a personality trait

The sub-scale "Tolerance as a personal trait" largely determines personal characteristics, views and beliefs, a person's personal attitude to the environment.

CONCLUSIONS

Our research revealed that the sub-scales "Ethnic tolerance" and "Tolerance as a personality trait" are correlated with the sub-scale "Social tolerance" in students. Therefore, students with personal tolerance show more tolerance in situations related to ethnic processes. This indicates the need for research on the development of more social tolerance in students.

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